

Physical characteristics of hemp (*Cannabis sativa L.*) seeds and thermal processing effect on nutritional and functional properties

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Received: Dec 15, 2025

Accepted: Jan 10, 2026

Published: Jan 14, 2026

Abstract

Hemp (*Cannabis sativa L.*) seeds are well known for being high nutritious and have good functional potential in food systems. This study assessed the physical characteristics of whole hemp seeds and inspected the effect of processing techniques (roasted and steamed) on the functional properties and proximate composition of hemp seed flour. Physical characteristics such as seed dimensions, surface area, sphericity, porosity and density were determined. Functional properties and proximate composition including water absorption capacity, oil absorption capacity, bulk density and swelling capacity were analysed using standard methods. Processing significantly influenced the functional attributes and nutritional properties of hemp seeds. Roasted hemp seed flour exhibited higher protein (39.15%), fat (34.94%) and energy (504.40 kcal/100g) values, while steamed hemp seed flour showed enhanced water absorption (1.53%) and swelling capacity (5.46 ml/g). The physical property data generated are relevant for post harvested handling and processing equipment design. Overall, the results demonstrate that hemp seeds are a nutrient dense raw material and appropriate processing can enhance their functional suitability for food product development.

Keywords: hemp seed flour, physical properties, thermal treatment, functional properties, proximate composition

Introduction

In the past few years, new functional and nutraceutical foods have emerged as society is compelled to eat healthy foods. Thus, health-promoting food-products are becoming the focal point is not only to satisfy the consumer's hunger but also to fill up the deficit in nutrients and maintain physical and mental well-being [1]. Nowadays, there is an increased consumption of hemp seeds and derivative food products, especially among vegans. While whole hemp seeds can be consumed as food, they are primarily used as raw material for development of other products such as hemp seed flour, oil, and protein [2].

Hemp (*Cannabis sativa L.*) is a globally cultivated ancient plant, typically an annual herb, renowned for its fiber, medicinal, psychoactive and nutritional properties [3]. Hempseed represents a rich array of essential fatty acids, fibers, minerals, and vitamins, along with a good amount of essential amino acids, lipids, and because of their nutritional properties hemp seeds and their products are achieving growing popularity as food for humans [4]. The hempseed amino acid profile is deemed equivalent to that of egg white and soybeans, with a substantial quantity of sulfur containing amino acids, which are notably absent in legumes in adequate amounts [5]. Because of their superior nutritional content, these foods have demonstrated beneficial health effects including reduced cholesterol and high blood pressure, and are now widely used for both animal and human consumption [6].

With growing adaptability of hemp seeds, there is a need to exploit processing mechanisms and efficiently store hemp seeds [3] because hemp seeds have a considerable amount of protein, and their bioactive nutritional composition is highly sensitive and requires special storage facilities. Physical characteristics, such as size, shape, and weight of the seeds, need to be well defined to carry out the cleaning, handling, separating, grading, storing, milling, and packaging processes involved with hemp processed seeds [7]. The physical characteristics of grains/seeds are vital for the design and construction of both storage and processing machinery, as well as for addressing machine design issues and the behaviour of products during all agricultural processes, including planting, harvesting, threshing, handling, sorting, and drying.

Physical characteristics like dimensions, weight, volume, density, porosity and surface area are key factors in how products are graded. Sorting products by their size helps reduce cost of packaging and transportation, and make it easier to choose the right packaging materials [8]. Length, width and thickness determination is helpful while designing tools like seed planters, sorting machines, pneumatic conveying systems and farming equipment. The shape of the product to be packed is important for preparing them for automated processes such as peeling, removing cores and pits, and positioning them in packaging machines [9]. Measuring linear size and colour values are important for creating sorting and grading equipments. Estimation of the bulk density is useful to determine the capacity of storage and transport of the products, while true density is used to design effective separation equipments. Porosity determines the resistance to airflow during aeration and drying operations. Differences between varieties are also one of a major reason for having deviations in physical properties [10].

The functional properties of foods ingredients are influenced by means of the various components that are proteins, fibre, fats and oils, carbohydrates, moisture, ash, and other ingredients or food additives that are added to the food. Although two or more components may have the same effect, one may even have a minor effect on a functional property. Mycotoxins such as patulin in grains may also affect the functional properties of flours. Functional properties are very important for food quality [11]. Despite increasing interest in hemp based foods, limited studies have simultaneously evaluated the physical properties of whole hemp seeds and the effect of thermal processing methods on the functional and proximate characteristics of hemp seed flour. Therefore, the present study aimed to investigate physical properties of whole hemp seeds, determine the effect of roasting and steaming on the proximate composition of hemp seed flour and assess the functional properties of raw and processed hemp seed flour.

Material and methods

1. Sample collection and processing

Hemp seeds were procured from local markets of cities in Uttarakhand. The seeds were cleaned manually to remove foreign matter, broken and immature seeds. Raw seeds were processed by roasting (150°C for 30 min) and steaming (155°C for 45 min). After processing, seeds were cooled to room temperature and grounded into fine flour with the help of electrical mixer grinder. At last seed powder was stored in air tight container for further analysis.

2. Physical properties of whole seeds

The initial moisture content of whole seeds (equation 1) was determined by drying 5g sample in triplicate at 105±1°C for 24h using the hot air oven method [12]. Seed mass was determined by weighing 100 manually counted seeds with an accuracy of 0.001g using a digital weighing machine in triplicate. The physical dimension of 100 randomly selected seeds were determined in terms of length (L/major axis), width (W/intermediate axis, perpendicular to length), and thickness (T/minor axis, perpendicular to length and width) using a digital vernier calliper, with an accuracy of 0.01mm. the geometric mean diameter, DG, arithmetic mean diameter, DA, square mean diameter, DS, and sphericity, SP were determined by standard methods [13] using equations (2), (3), (4) and (5), considering the spheroid shape of seeds. Volume, V and Surface area, S of seeds were found by analogy with a sphere of the same geometric mean diameter, represented by the equation (6) and (7) [14].

$$\text{Moisture} = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where,

W_1 = Initial weight of dish with sample

W_2 = Final weight of dish with dried sample

W = Weight of sample

$$DG = (L \times W \times T)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (2)$$

$$DA = \frac{L+W+T}{3} \quad (3)$$

$$DS = \sqrt{L \times L + W \times W + T \times T} \quad (4)$$

$$SP = \frac{(L \times W \times T)^{\frac{1}{3}}}{L} \quad (5)$$

$$V = \frac{\pi}{6} (DG)^3 \quad (6)$$

$$S = \pi DG^2 \quad (7)$$

The bulk density, BD (8) (g cm^{-3}) was determined by weight and volume ratio, while the true density, TD (9) (g cm^{-3}) was determined using the toluene displacement technique. Using bulk and true density values, porosity, P (%) was calculated using the formula given in equation 10 [10].

$$BD = \frac{\text{Weight of sample}}{\text{Volume occupied}} \quad (8)$$

$$TD = \frac{\text{Weight of sample}}{\text{Volume of toluene displaced}} \quad (9)$$

$$P = \left(1 - \frac{\text{Bulk density}}{\text{True density}}\right) \times 100 \quad (10)$$

3. Proximate nutrient composition

Moisture was determined by desiccation at $105\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ till constant weight was observed. Total Ash was determined by using muffle furnace at $550\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$. Protein content was determined while using the Kjeldhal method and total nitrogen was converted to protein using the nitrogen-protein conversion factor 6.25. Fat content was determined by Soxhlet extraction and petroleum ether was used as the solvent, and fibre content was also observed according to the guidelines given by AOAC [12]. Available carbohydrate content was determined by the difference i.e. subtracting the sum of the values of moisture, ash, protein, fat, and fibre from hundred. Energy values were calculated using the following conversion factors: 4kcal/g for proteins and carbohydrates, 9kcal/g for fat, and 2kcal/g for fibre. The result of this calculation is expressed in kcal/100g.

4. Functional properties of flours

Water absorption capacity, W_{ac} (equation 11), oil absorption capacity, O_{ac} (equation 12), and bulk density (equation 13) was determined following the method discussed by Kaur, et al. [15]. WAC was measured by mixing 1g sample with 10ml distilled water in a centrifuge tube, agitated for 1 min, and shaken at $24\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 min. the mixture was then centrifuged at 3700 rpm for 25 min, the supernatant was measured. OAC was determined by mixing 500mg sample with 12 ml soyabean oil and held at $24\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 min. The mixture was centrifuged at 3700 rpm for 25 min, and the supernatant was measured. For measuring bulk density, 50g flour sample was placed in a 200ml measuring cylinder and tapped repeatedly until a constant volume was reached. The final volume was recorded to calculate bulk density.

$$W_{ac} = \frac{\text{Volume of water absorbed}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \quad (11)$$

$$O_{ac} = \frac{\text{Volume of oil absorbed}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Bulk density} = \frac{\text{Weight of sample}}{\text{Volume of sample after tapping}} \quad (13)$$

Swelling capacity was measured using the method of Cotovanu & Mironeasa [16]. 1g of flour was mixed with 10ml water in a centrifuge tube and heated in a water bath at 80°C for 15 min. After centrifugation at 2000 rpm for 30 min, the supernatant was decanted, and the volume of the swollen pellet was recorded. S_c was expressed as the volume ml per gram of sample.

5. Statistical analysis

All experimental data were recorded electronically and was analyzed using IBM SPSS 20.0 Version Statistics Software. The results are presented as mean and standard deviation (Mean \pm SD) wherever needed.

Results and discussion

1. Physical properties of whole seed

The dimensional and gravimetric characteristics of whole hemp seeds are presented in table 1 and 2. The mean length, width and thickness of the seeds were recorded as $4.00\pm 0.03\text{mm}$, $3.30\pm 0.03\text{mm}$ and $2.80\pm 0.02\text{mm}$ respectively, indicating relatively uniform seed size. Such uniformity is advantageous for shorting, grading and mechanical handling operations, as dimensional consistency improves the efficiency of clening, separation and milling equipment [8], [9]. The arithmetic ($3.40\pm 0.02\text{mm}$) and geometric ($3.30\pm 0.02\text{mm}$) mean diameter reflecting the overall size distribution of the seeds, and were comparable to values reported for industrial hemp seeds at similar moisture levels [7], [17].

The sphericity of hemp seeds was found to be $83.30\pm 0.04\%$, indicating a near spherical shape, which is favorable for flow-ability during conveying and storage, as seeds with near-spherical geometry encounter less resistance during movement [10]. Similar sphericity values have been reported for different hemp cultivars, although variations have been attributed to varietal differences and growing conditions [24], [26]. The mean surface area ($35.23\pm 0.05 \text{mm}^2$) suggests favourable heat and mass transfer during roasting and thermal processing [17].

Table 1: Dimensional Properties of Hemp Seeds

Physical properties	No. of observations	Unit of measurements	Minimum value	Maximum value	Mean \pm SD
Length	100	mm	2.80	4.90	4.00 \pm 0.03
Width	100	mm	2.30	4.20	3.30 \pm 0.03
Thickness	100	mm	1.80	3.80	2.80 \pm 0.02
Arithmetic mean diameter	100	mm	2.60	3.90	3.40 \pm 0.02
Geometric mean diameter	100	mm	2.50	3.80	3.30 \pm 0.02
Square mean diameter	100	mm	4.60	6.90	5.90 \pm 0.05
Sphericity	100	%	75.00	98.00	83.30 \pm 0.04
Surface area	100	mm ²	20.00	47.00	35.23 \pm 0.05

Results from the gravimetric assessment show that the moisture content of the entire seed (seeds) is $8.3 \pm 0.10\%$ which is within the acceptable moisture ranges for long term oil seed (oil seed) storage. This also decreases the chance of oxidation of lipids and microbial infection [3]. The mass (weight) of the 100 seeds is 1.90 ± 0.01 gm and the volume is 18.82 ± 0.11 cc. The observed bulk and true density values for the seeds were 557.5 ± 0.02 kgm^{-3} and 1043.00 ± 0.07 kgm^{-3} respectively. The porosity of the seeds based on the bulk density and true density was determined to be $46.50 \pm 1.5\%$, which indicates that a relatively large fraction of the seed is occupied by pores. This porosity will provide a significant amount of aeration, allowing moisture to be easily lost from the seed mass during drying and improved air circulation throughout the seed in storage [7]. Similar ranges for porosity and density have been observed for hemp seeds as well as other oilseeds such as chia where the degree of moisture content and varietal differences greatly impact porosity and density values [18]. The present study results support the potential of utilizing hemp seeds for post harvest handling and storage systems.

Table 2: Gravimetric Properties of hemp seeds

Physical properties	No. of observation	Unit of measurements	mean \pm SD
Moisture	3	%	8.3 \pm 0.10
Hundred seed mass	10	g	1.90 \pm 0.01
Hundred seed volume	10	mm ³	18.82 \pm 0.11
Bulk density	3	kgm ⁻³	557.50 \pm 0.02
True density	3	kgm ⁻³	1043.00 \pm 0.07
Porosity	3	%	46.50 \pm 1.5

2. Functional properties of flour

The functional properties of wheat flour and raw, roasted and steamed hemp seed flours are presented in Table 3. Swelling capacity varied significantly amongst the samples. Steamed hemp seed flour had the highest value at 5.46 ± 0.35 ml/g, followed by raw hemp seed flour at 4.23 ± 0.25 ml/g, roasted hemp seed flour at 3.36 ± 0.40 ml/g and lowest value for wheat flour at 2.03 ± 0.25 ml/g. This increased swelling behavior is linked to starch gelatinization and protein unfolding during steaming. These processes enhance the availability of hydrophilic sites that can bind water [11]. Similar improvements in swelling and hydration properties due to moist heat processing have been observed in thermally processed cereal and pseudo cereal flours [19].

The swelling capacity of raw hemp seed flour is greater than roasted hemp seed flour's. Roasted hemp seed flour has significantly less swelling capacity than other samples of hemp seed flour. Roasting reduces the swelling capacity of hemp seed flour because roasting increases protein aggregation in hemp seeds and dry heat makes the structure more rigid; thus limiting the water's ability to penetrate the flour matrix [13]. Compared to hemp seed flours, wheat flour has the least swelling ability due to its lower protein and higher cellulose content than hemp seed flours [15].

The highest WAC of all was shown in steamed hemp seed flour ($1.53 \pm 0.11\%$) with roasted hemp seed flour having the second highest ($1.50 \pm 0.10\%$) and wheat flour tied for the second highest ($1.50 \pm 0.00\%$). An increased WAC is indicative of enhanced hydration behavior of steamed flour which improves the development of dough and the resulting texture of the product in various formulations [16]. On the other hand, raw hemp seed flour showed lower WAC, probably because of intact protein and starch structures which limits water uptake.

The highest value of oil absorption capacity (OAC) was found in wheat flour ($1.60 \pm 0.00\%$), followed by raw and steamed hemp seed flours exhibiting similar values ($1.46 \pm 0.30\%$) and roasted hemp seed flour showed lowest value at $1.26 \pm 0.30\%$. The relatively lower OAC of roasted hemp seed flour may be attributed to heat-induced protein denaturation and decreased availability of non-polar amino acid side chains that are responsible for oil binding [11]. Bulk density values were ranged from 0.26g/cc to 0.30 g/cc, in which steamed hemp seed flour exhibited the highest bulk density, indicating tighter particle packing. Flours with a higher bulk density flours take up less space and volume, and could be advantageous for storage and packaging purpose [15].

Table 3: Functional properties of wheat flour and hemp seed flours

Sample	Swelling capacity (ml/g)	Water absorption capacity (%)	Oil absorption capacity (%)	Bulk density (g/cc)
Wheat flour	2.03 \pm 0.25	1.50 \pm 0.00	1.60 \pm 0.00	0.26 \pm 0.00
Raw seed flour	4.23 \pm 0.25	1.03 \pm 0.15	1.46 \pm 0.30	0.28 \pm 0.00
Roasted seed flour	3.36 \pm 0.40	1.50 \pm 0.10	1.26 \pm 0.30	0.28 \pm 0.00
Steam seed flour	5.46 \pm 0.35	1.53 \pm 0.11	1.46 \pm 0.30	0.30 \pm 0.00

3. Proximate composition

The proximate composition of wheat and hemp seed flours subjected to different processing treatments is summarized in table 4. The moisture content of steamed hemp seed flour ($9.62 \pm 0.21\%$) was found to be highest followed by wheat flour ($8.58 \pm 0.85\%$), raw hemp seed flour ($7.21 \pm 0.10\%$) and roasted hemp seed flour ($4.13 \pm 0.15\%$). Total ash content recorder highest in roasted

hemp seed flour ($6.83\pm 0.40\%$), then raw ($33.98\pm 1.37\%$) and steamed ($5.65\pm 0.45\%$) hemp seed flour and highest in wheat flour ($0.93\pm 0.40\%$). Hemp seed flours exhibited substantially higher protein and fat contents than wheat flour, confirming hemp seeds as a nutrient-dense raw material. Roasted hemp seed flour showed the highest protein content ($34.94\pm 1.12\%$) and fat content ($34.94\pm 1.12\%$), which can be attributed to moisture loss during roasting, leading to concentration of nutrients. Similar protein and lipid ranges have been reported for industrial hemp seeds and their processed fractions [6], [20], [21].

Based on the findings of this study, protein content found in hemp seed are in agreement with the prior publications indicating that the protein from hemp seeds has a high digestibility and are rich in edestin and albumin protein fractions [4], [5]. The moisture content for steamed hempseed flour was greater than that of raw hempseed flour, and also the fat content and energy value of steamed hempseed flour appears to be slightly less than raw hempseed flour, possibly due to the moisture uptake during steaming and partial leaching of water during steaming. Other researchers have also reported similar effects of moist heat application to other oilseed and cereal flours on their proximate composition [22].

Crude fibre content showed minor variation among hemp seed flours, ranging from $6.53\pm 0.43\%$ to $6.73\pm 0.37\%$, indicating that fibre components are largely resistant to moderate thermal processing. Available carbohydrate content decreased with processing, with raw hemp seed flour containing the highest value ($12.86\pm 1.66\%$) and roasted hemp seed flour the lowest ($8.31\pm 1.52\%$), reflecting possible thermal degradation and redistribution of carbohydrate fractions, a trend also reported in earlier compositional studies of hemp seeds [22], [23]. The energy values were highest recorded for roasted hemp seeds flour (504.40 ± 5.94 kcal/100g), consistent with its higher fat content. Variability in nutrient composition among hemp seed flour is in agreement with previous studies emphasizing the influence of cultivar, growing conditions and processing methods [21], [24], [25].

Table 4: Proximate composition of wheat flour and hemp seed flours

Sample	Moisture (%)	Total ash (%)	Crude protein (%)	Crude fat (%)	Crude fibre (%)	Carbohydrate rate (%)	Energy (Kcal/100g)
Wheat flour	8.58 ± 0.85	0.93 ± 0.40	10.72 ± 1.43	1.44 ± 0.77	2.83 ± 0.78	52.22 ± 1.82	264.80 ± 2.33
Raw seed flour	7.21 ± 0.10	6.26 ± 0.11	33.98 ± 1.37	32.93 ± 0.84	6.73 ± 0.37	12.86 ± 1.66	483.78 ± 6.40
Roasted seed flour	4.13 ± 0.15	6.83 ± 0.40	39.15 ± 2.19	34.94 ± 1.12	6.61 ± 0.53	8.31 ± 1.52	504.40 ± 5.94
Steam seed flour	9.62 ± 0.21	5.65 ± 0.45	35.72 ± 3.12	30.74 ± 0.67	6.53 ± 0.43	11.72 ± 4.20	466.47 ± 2.70

Conclusion

Study results show that hemp seeds have favorable characteristics that are important to harvest, handle, store, and process after harvest. The data has been used to establish a baseline of data regarding size and weight measurements for the development of equipment to optimize the theoretical design and operation of processing operations. Hemp seeds have varying densities, shapes, and porosities that will allow for maximum efficiency when using equipment for cleaning, grading, transporting, and milling.

There are several important ways that the processing method has altered the proximate composition and functional properties of hemp seed flour. Roasting increased the levels of protein, fat, and energy, making roasted hemp seed flour a viable source for the development of high-quality food products. Steaming has resulted in an increase in functional properties such as water and swelling capacity which impact how a food product's texture and stability will be affected. The differences among raw, roasted, and steamed treatments clearly demonstrate the practice of how processing can impact both nutritional quality as well as functional capabilities.

Overall, hemp seeds represent a nutritionally rich and functionally versatile raw material. Appropriate selection of processing techniques can tailor hemp seed flour for specific food applications, supporting its potential use in functional, fortified and value added food products.

Acknowledgement

The authors sincerely acknowledge the support and facilities provided by the division of Food Science and Nutrition, Banasthali Vidyapith, Rajasthan, India, for carrying out the present research. The authors are also grateful to the faculty members and technical staff of the department for their assistance during sample processing, laboratory analysis and data interpretation. The authors would like to thank all individuals who contributed directly or indirectly to the successful completion of the study.

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